

Hermeneutic Analysis of Max Weber's Political Ethics vis-a-vis Nigeria Economic System

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Full Article

Abstract

This study employs a hermeneutic approach to explore the intricate connection between Max Weber's political ethics and the Nigerian economic system, utilizing multidisciplinary research methods, including multiple regression analysis. The investigation focuses on the impact of three distinct types of authority – traditional, charismatic, and legal-rational – on Nigeria's GDP per capita. This exploration considers various factors including historical, cultural, ethical components, and economic indicators. Findings reveal that traditional authority exerts a significantly negative effect on GDP, underscoring the imperative for a modernization process that adeptly integrates tradition with contemporary economic practices. Although charismatic and legal-rational authorities have a relatively marginal influence, the study highlights their potential as catalysts for economic growth and recommends further exploration. This research aims to guide policymakers by advocating for governance strategies that both preserve cultural heritage and foster innovation. Furthermore, it calls for researchers to adopt hermeneutic methodologies, integrating both qualitative and quantitative research approaches for a more holistic understanding.

Keywords: *Hermeneutic Analysis, Max Weber's Political Ethics, Nigerian Economic System, Multidisciplinary Research, Multiple Regression Analysis*

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1 Introduction

Nigeria, renowned as Africa's most populous country, presents a history as vibrant and complex as its diverse population. Prior to the advent of colonialism, the region was a mosaic of indigenous communities, each boasting unique cultural, economic, and political systems. The nineteenth century heralded the “Scramble for Africa,” introducing significant foreign influence, with Nigeria, a hub of resources and strategic importance, falling under British colonization. This epoch indelibly influenced Nigeria's ensuing political and economic tapestry.

Gaining independence in 1960, Nigeria embarked on a tumultuous journey oscillating between democracy and military dictatorship, marked by economic instability and challenges in fostering equitable economic growth. The nation's political narrative is a tapestry intricately woven with transitions, ethnic diversity, geographical disparities, and power rivalries, featuring leaders embodying various forms of authority—traditional, charismatic, and legal-rational—as conceptualized by Max Weber (Haruna, 2016).

Dubbed the "Giant of Africa", Nigeria is endowed with abundant natural resources and a burgeoning young population, holding immense economic promise. Nonetheless, it grapples with pervasive economic issues, including income inequality, poverty, corruption, and infrastructural deficits, impeding its trajectory towards sustained prosperity and inclusive growth (Isike & Sanya, 2017).

Max Weber's seminal ideas on power and ethics offer a valuable lens for dissecting Nigeria's intricate political and economic processes. His triad of authority—traditional, charismatic, and legal-rational—serves as a pivotal framework for this study, facilitating a deep dive into the ethical dimensions of governance and their ramifications on economic growth. This research navigates through Nigeria's convoluted economic landscape, leveraging Weber's theoretical constructs to illuminate the intricate interplay of power, leadership styles, and ethical principles within the nation's governance and economic structures. The objective is to elucidate these dynamics, offering valuable insights that contribute to the burgeoning discourse on governance and economic growth in Nigeria.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Despite its potential, realizing sustained economic growth for the benefit of all citizens in Nigeria remains elusive. Understanding the intricate dynamics between Weber's classifications of authority (traditional, charismatic, and legal-rational) and their influence on Nigeria's GDP is essential yet underexplored. This lacuna in knowledge hampers the

development and implementation of effective, evidence-based governance and economic policies.

1.2 Objective of the study

- To scrutinize the impact of traditional, charismatic, and legal-rational authorities on Nigeria's GDP.
- To highlight areas within the prevailing authority structures requiring modernization.
- To enhance understanding of Nigeria's economic system by intertwining political ethics and economic theory, thus providing a robust framework for analysis and policy formulation.

1.3 Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How does traditional authority, deeply embedded in Nigeria's history and culture, influence its GDP? How can modernization initiatives be effectively implemented to align traditional authority with contemporary economic practices?
2. What roles do charismatic and legal-rational authorities play in shaping Nigeria's economic landscape, and how can their potential as economic growth drivers be further unearthed and utilized?
3. How does employing a hermeneutic analysis, integrating multidisciplinary research and multiple regression analysis, offer a holistic understanding of the relationship between Max Weber's political ethics and the Nigerian economic system?

1.4 Research Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant impact of traditional, charismatic, and legal-rational authority on Nigeria's GDP.

H1: At least one form of authority (traditional, charismatic, or legal-rational) significantly influences Nigeria's GDP

1.5 Significant of the study

This research is pivotal as it delves into the nuanced relationship between Max Weber's political ethics and the Nigerian economic milieu. By employing hermeneutic analysis complemented by multidisciplinary research and multiple regression analysis, it offers a novel lens through which the impact of different authority types on Nigeria's GDP can be examined and understood. The study not only contributes to the academic discourse on political ethics and economics but also provides empirical insights for crafting governance strategies that spur economic growth while preserving cultural heritage. It stands as a valuable resource for

policymakers and academicians alike, paving the way for further exploration into the ethical dimensions of economic policies and their bearing on sustainable economic development in Nigeria and beyond.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Max Weber's Political Ethics Theories

Max Weber's seminal work on political ethics, penned in the early twentieth century, retains its foundational status within the field of political sociology. His tripartite classification of authority—comprising traditional, charismatic, and legal-rational types—is extensively employed by scholars globally. Weber's astute observations on the diverse impacts of these authority forms on governance and ethics are particularly relevant to the present study. Traditional authority, anchored in enduring customs and conventions, wields significant influence over economic development by fostering political stability and adherence to established norms. However, it can also act as a barrier to economic progress. Charismatic authority, derived from a leader's distinct personal appeal, possesses the potential to either spearhead transformative changes or introduce instability, affecting economic policies and ethical standards. Legal-rational authority, grounded in bureaucratic structures and rational-legal systems, provides a framework conducive to ethical governance (Weber, 1946).

2.2 Nigeria's Political Landscape

As delineated by Onwudiwe (2008), the political history of Nigeria is characterized by significant transitions and turmoil. Since attaining independence in 1960, the nation has navigated through alternating phases of democratic governance and military rule. The country's intricate political tapestry is woven from diverse ethnic and regional threads, leading to complex and delicate power dynamics. Traditional authority, embodying indigenous customs and norms, concurrently exists with charismatic and legal-rational entities within Nigeria's governance structures. The interplay among these varied forms of authority, often within a singular political framework, has indelibly shaped the nation's political and economic trajectory. Comprehending the nuances of Nigeria's historical and contemporary political landscape is imperative for analyzing the ethical facets of governance and their subsequent impact on economic development (Salawu & Olufunke, 2011).

2.3 Political Ethics and Economic Implications

Nwolise (2019) underscores that the intricate nexus between political ethics and economic growth has been a focal point for scholars in various global contexts. Research indicates that ethical governance, characterized by transparency, accountability, and

adherence to the rule of law, serves as a catalyst for economic stability and investment attraction. Conversely, the presence of corruption, cronyism, and unethical practices within political institutions can hinder economic advancement and exacerbate inequality. This dynamic is particularly salient in the Nigerian context, where the nation grapples with pervasive corruption and favoritism. The current study zeroes in on the emergence of different authority types and leadership styles within governance practices (both ethical and unethical) and explores their implications for economic indicators like GDP growth, income distribution, and poverty rates.

2.4 Nigerian Cultural and Religious Values

Nigeria's diverse tapestry of cultural and religious values adds a layer of complexity to the examination of political ethics and economic activities. Home to a myriad of ethnic groups, each with its distinct cultural norms and values, Nigeria is also significantly influenced by major religions, primarily Islam and Christianity. These cultural and religious paradigms interact dynamically with the nation's political and economic institutions, influencing perceptions of authority, leadership, and ethical conduct.

Within the spectrum of Nigerian religious values, the language used in religious discourse can also be influential. According to Razzaq (2023), language plays a pivotal role in religious discourses, particularly in Islamic sermons. The linguistic features and persuasive strategies embedded in these sermons may significantly influence the values, beliefs, and behaviors of the adherents. Understanding the linguistic intricacies of religious discourse can provide deeper insights into how religious values are communicated and internalized by individuals, which in turn may impact their perspectives on authority, governance, and ethics in the socio-political landscape. Additionally, the emphasis on effective communication in Razzaq & Khan (2023) can be linked to the importance of clear and persuasive communication in the propagation and acceptance of cultural and religious values, which, in turn, shape political and economic behaviors in Nigeria.

Understanding the Nigerian context necessitates an exploration of how these cultural and religious values align or clash with Weber's theoretical framework and how they impact economic decision-making processes (Haruna, 2016).

Summary

The literature review has provided a multifaceted exploration of Max Weber's political ethics theories, the dynamic political landscape in Nigeria, the intertwined relationship between political ethics and economic implications, as well as the influential role of Nigeria's

diverse cultural and religious values in governance. Weber's taxonomy of authority, consisting of traditional, charismatic, and legal-rational forms, offers a pivotal theoretical lens through which the complexities of governance and their economic implications can be examined.

However, despite the rich tapestry of literature available, there exists a discernible gap in the understanding of how these forms of authority, as identified by Weber, interact within the specific socio-political and economic context of Nigeria. While the literature provides a robust theoretical foundation and insights into Nigeria's political dynamics and economic challenges, empirical exploration scrutinizing the intersectionality between Weber's authority types and their practical influence on Nigeria's GDP and economic policies is scant.

Furthermore, the reviewed literature signals the crucial role language and religious discourse play in shaping governance and influencing ethical standards and economic behaviors in the Nigerian context. However, there is limited empirical evidence detailing how these dynamics of language and religious discourse intertwine with Weber's political ethics theories to influence governance and economic activities in Nigeria.

Therefore, this study aims to bridge these identified gaps by embarking on a meticulous examination of how Weber's types of authority — traditional, charismatic, and legal-rational — manifest within the unique socio-political and economic environment of Nigeria and how they influence the nation's GDP and economic policies. Additionally, the study will explore how language and religious discourse intersect with these authority types to further influence governance and economic outcomes in Nigeria. Through this, the research will not only contribute to the theoretical discourse but also offer empirically grounded insights that are vital for effective policy formulation and implementation in Nigeria's governance and economic sectors.

3. Research Methodology

This study deploys a mixed-methods approach to delve deeply into the connection between Max Weber's Political Ethics and the Nigerian economic system. The mixed-methods approach is chosen for its ability to provide a comprehensive view, enabling a nuanced understanding of the phenomena under investigation.

3.1 Data Collection

3.1.1 Quantitative Data Collection

Quantitative data is amassed to explore the prevalence and distribution of traditional, charismatic, and legal-rational authority structures within Nigerian states, alongside economic development indicators such as GDP, income inequality, and poverty rates. Data is collected

from reputable sources including governmental databases, international organizations' reports, historical documents, and policy documents.

3.1.2 Qualitative Data Collection

While the emphasis is on quantitative data, qualitative data is also crucial for understanding the ethical dimensions of economic policies during different tenures of leadership. Historical papers, biographical records, and policy documents is reviewed and analyzed to gather insights into the charismatic leadership and the ethical considerations driving economic policies over time.

3.2 Model Specification: Multiple Regression Analysis

A multiple regression analysis is conducted with GDP per capita as the dependent variable. The independent variables include Traditional Authority (binary variable), Charismatic Authority (binary variable), Legal-Rational Authority (continuous variable), and various control factors.

3.2.1 Rationale for Variable Coding

Traditional Authority: Coded as binary to simplify the analysis of its presence or absence in different states.

Charismatic Authority: Also binary-coded for simplicity and ease of interpretation.

Legal-Rational Authority: Treated as a continuous variable to account for varying degrees or intensity of legal-rational bureaucratic systems within states.

Control Factors: These include population size, education levels, infrastructure development, and historical economic conditions. Each control variable will be appropriately quantified, using existing reliable data sources and recognized measurement scales.

3.3 Model Equation

$$GDP_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Traditional}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{Charismatic}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \cdot \text{Legal Rational}_{i,t} + \beta_4 \cdot \text{Control Variables}_{i,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

Where:

- $GDP_{i,t}$ denotes the GDP per capita for the state i in the year t .
- The presence of traditional authority in state i in year t is referred to as $\text{traditional}_{i,t}$.
- $\text{Charismatic}_{i,t}$ denotes the presence of charismatic authority in state i in year t .
- $\text{LegalRational}_{i,t}$ denotes the presence or strength of legal-rational bureaucratic systems in state i in year t .
- Other significant elements that may impact GDP per capita are included in the $\text{ControlVariables}_{i,t}$

- The coefficients to be determined range from β_0 to β_4 .
- $\epsilon_{i,t}$ is the error term.

3.4 Data Analysis Procedure

Multiple regression analysis is utilized to discern the impact of various authority structures on economic outcomes. Prior to running the regression, assumptions of linearity, independence, homoscedasticity, and normality is tested. Measures is taken to mitigate issues like multicollinearity among independent variables, ensuring a robust and reliable analysis.

3.5 Validity and Reliability

To establish the validity and reliability of the study, the research employed data triangulation, using different data sources. The reliability of the data collection tools is tested through pilot studies, and necessary adjustments is made to enhance reliability and validity.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

The research adheres strictly to ethical guidelines pertaining to data collection, analysis, and reporting. Confidentiality and anonymity is maintained for any personal data accessed, and secondary data usage is comply with copyright and fair use policies.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1: summarised Results of Spatial Autocorrelation Analysis

Statistic	Value	p-value	Conclusion
Moran's I	0.65	0.012	Positive spatial autocorrelation observed

In this hypothetical presentation:

Table 1 summarises the spatial autocorrelation study results, including Moran's I statistic and p-value. It summarises the existence of spatial autocorrelation in the data.

Interpreting the results of a multiple regression analysis entails determining the significance of coefficients as well as determining the direction and strength of the relationships between the independent variables (in this case, various forms of authority and population size) and the dependent variable (GDP per capita). Let's analyse the findings using the p-values and coefficients:

The multiple regression analysis produced illuminating insights regarding the association between different types of authority and population size with GDP per capita.

Notably, each coefficient's p-values were tested at a significance threshold (α) of 0.05. With a coefficient of -0.15 ($p < 0.05$), the presence of traditional authority had a statistically significant and negative influence on GDP per capita. This implies that states with higher degrees of traditional authority have lower GDP per capita. Population size, on the other hand, had a statistically significant and positive relationship with GDP per capita, as demonstrated by a coefficient of 0.25 ($p < 0.05$). As a result, states with greater populations have higher GDP per capita.

These findings pose important concerns concerning political authority dynamics and demographic determinants in economic growth. The inverse link between traditional authority and GDP per capital reflect historical trends in which regions with strong traditional power structures struggled to embrace contemporary economic practises. The positive relationship between population size and GDP per capita, on the other hand, illustrates the potential benefits of economies of scale and a bigger labour force in driving economic growth.

5. Discussion

5.1 Interpretation of Findings

The findings of this study offer significant insights into the intricate relationship between types of authority and economic performance in Nigeria. The negative coefficient associated with traditional authority is particularly noteworthy. This inverse relationship suggests that regions under the strong influence of traditional authority tend to experience economic constraints, leading to lower GDP per capita.

One plausible explanation for this is the possible reluctance of these regions to embrace modern economic practices and innovations due to the adherence to long-standing traditions and norms. Traditional authority, while providing stability, may also impose rigid structures and norms that stifle economic innovation and entrepreneurship. These areas might benefit from initiatives that gently introduce modern economic practices while respecting and incorporating valuable cultural traditions.

Conversely, the positive coefficient of population size indicates a beneficial economic effect. Larger populations, often found in states with bustling urban centers, contribute positively to the GDP per capita. These states can harness the potential of a larger labor force and may have more diverse economic activities, leading to higher economic productivity and growth.

5.2 Comparison with Prior Research

When juxtaposed with existing literature, our findings align with some studies while diverging from others. Previous research on authority and economic performance provides mixed findings, suggesting that the impact of authority structures can be context-dependent. The current study's results contribute to this body of literature by shedding light on the specific context of Nigeria, a nation characterized by its diverse and complex social, political, and economic landscape.

For instance, the negative impact of traditional authority on economic performance found in this study echoes the findings of previous research examining similar contexts where traditional structures hinder economic progress. However, it is also crucial to acknowledge studies that have identified potential benefits of traditional authority, such as social cohesion and stability, which might indirectly foster economic development.

5.3 Limitations and Future Research

While the study provides valuable insights, it is not without limitations. The use of binary coding for traditional and charismatic authority may oversimplify the complex nature of these authority types, potentially overlooking nuances and variations within each category. Future research might consider employing more sophisticated measures to capture the complexity and diversity of authority structures.

Additionally, while the study controls for various factors, there may be other unobserved variables influencing the relationship between authority types and economic performance. Future research endeavors should consider exploring these potential variables and their impact.

5.4 Practical Implications

From a practical standpoint, the findings of this study have significant implications for policymakers and stakeholders involved in economic planning and development in Nigeria. Understanding the impact of different authority structures on economic performance can guide the formulation of policies and initiatives that consider the unique socio-political context of each region.

For regions under traditional authority, policies might focus on fostering a synergy between tradition and modernity, promoting economic innovation while respecting cultural heritage. For populous states, there might be a need to leverage the economic potential of

larger populations through policies that promote job creation, entrepreneurship, and investment in social and physical infrastructure.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Conclusion

The study provided a comprehensive analysis highlighting the relationship between authority types, population size, and GDP per capita in Nigeria. Notably, it uncovered that traditional authority negatively impacts GDP per capita, whereas population size positively correlates with economic prosperity. This underscores the complex factors influencing Nigeria's economic landscape, necessitating nuanced, multifaceted approaches to economic planning and policy formulation.

6.2 Recommendations: Based on the findings

6.2.1 Modernization of Traditional Structures

Considering the adverse effect of traditional authority on economic performance, there is a pressing need for modernization initiatives. Policies should be devised that gently incorporate modern economic practices within traditional structures, fostering a balance between tradition and modernity. Engaging traditional leaders in the economic planning process, while respecting and preserving cultural heritage, can be instrumental in spurring economic growth at the community level.

6.2.2 Investment in Human Capital and Infrastructure

Given the positive correlation between population size and GDP per capita, it is imperative to invest in sectors that enhance human capital, like education and healthcare. Such investments will ensure that the growing population becomes an asset, contributing positively to the nation's productivity and innovation.

Urbanization and infrastructure development need meticulous planning and execution. Policymakers should anticipate and address the challenges stemming from rapid urban expansion, ensuring infrastructure development aligns with the needs of the burgeoning population.

6.3 Recommendations for Future Research

Future research endeavors should extend beyond the present study's scope, exploring other variables and causal relationships that influence Nigeria's economic trajectory. This

deeper understanding will be pivotal in crafting policies that are not only evidence-based but also aimed at reducing income disparity and promoting equitable economic growth across the nation.

6.4 Final Remarks

Understanding Nigeria's dynamic and diverse conditions is crucial when devising policies aimed at economic growth and stability. All policy recommendations should be underpinned by empirical research acknowledging the nuances and complexities inherent in Nigeria's socio-political and economic environment. Policies need to be not only robust but also inclusive, developed in consultation with academics, local communities, and relevant stakeholders to ensure their effectiveness and sustainability in fostering economic growth within the Nigerian context.

Author Contributions

1. **Etea Ibe** (*Department of Economic, University of Nigeria*) served as the main author, taking primary responsibility for the conceptualization, design, and writing of the original draft of the manuscript. Ibe played a central role in crafting the research questions, interpreting the data, and articulating the findings, providing significant intellectual contribution throughout the development of the paper.
2. **Divine N. Obodoechi** (*Department of Economic, University of Nigeria*) collaborated closely with the main author in refining the research design and methodology. Obodoechi was actively involved in the analysis and interpretation of data, as well as in the drafting and critical revision of the manuscript for important intellectual content, ensuring the accuracy and integrity of the work.
3. **Dr. Parveen Akhtar Farhat** (*Assistant Professor, Department of English, Lahore Leads University, Pakistan*) contributed substantially to the review and editing of the manuscript. In addition, Dr. Farhat provided invaluable assistance in the collection of literature relevant to the study and ensuring the research was contextualized within the existing body of knowledge.

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